

Obtaining the Schrodinger Equation from the Fourier Series of a Potential

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Mathematically, it is possible to write a potential $V(x)$ in classical mechanics as a Fourier series. It is not guaranteed, however, that this series have any physical meaning. In this note, we argue that it has meaning if one thinks of the potential as an ensemble of different momentum sources, each with a different weight. Then, placing a particle in such a potential could yield an ensemble of momenta $f(p)$. This ensemble $W(x)$ at this point is not associated with a Fourier series, but it is an equilibrium ensemble and can also be thought of as a potential, it seems, which has different weights associated with different momenta. If this is the case, this ensemble can also be written as a Fourier series $W(x) = \sum_p f(p) \exp(ipx)$. Now, the ensemble $W(x)$ created by the potential $V(x)$ in the first place, can interact with the potential again and again. This can be described by writing $V(x)W(x)$. This combination should return the original ensemble $W(x)$ up to a constant if one has an equilibrium situation. Now $V(x) = \text{Energy} - \text{average Kinetic energy}$ which leads to the Schrodinger equation.

In classical mechanics, one considers the potential $V(x)$ as being associated with a force given by $-\text{grad } V(x)$ at a point x . One usually follows the trajectory of a particle, mapping v and dv/dt at each x at each time t . It is possible to write $V(x)$ as a Fourier series, but this may appear to be simply a mathematical exercise. If, however, one thinks of $V(x)$ as an ensemble of momentum sources then this might have meaning. Taking $-\text{grad}$ brings down a momentum term from each $\exp(ikx)$ which is proportional to the momentum imparted or dp/dt which is equal to the force. One is assuming an interaction in which the momentum from $V(x)$ interacts with a particle momentum k yielding only the particle with momentum $p+k$ by conservation of momentum.

If one considers a quantum type particle (or 2×2 matrix model particle [4] which has a wavelength and exists in a region of space), then there are various probabilities for this particle to interact with the various Fourier series terms of $V(x)$. This would lead to an ensemble if one cannot keep track of time exactly as in quantum mechanics and also the 2×2 matrix model [4]. At this point there is no Fourier series associated with the ensemble, simply $f(p, x)$.

Now, the ensemble appears as a source of different momenta with different weights. If this is the case, then the ensemble itself seems to act like a potential. The different momenta can interact with $V(x)$. For example, a momentum p from the ensemble might interact with a k from $V(x)$ to transform into $p+k$ by the conservation of momentum. Thus, it seems that one can write the ensemble $W(x)$ as a Fourier series as well namely $\sum_p f(p) \exp(ipx)$.

The interaction of $V(x)$ with $W(x)$ should give another potential like ensemble, but if there is equilibrium, this should be the same as the original $W(x)$ (created by $V(x)$) up to a constant. It is known from conservation of energy that $V(x) = E - \text{average KE}$ where E is the energy and KE the kinetic energy. Thus:

$$V(x)W(x) = (E - \text{average KE}) W(x)$$

It is possible to obtain average KE from $W(x)$ because its weights are relative probabilities and $1/2m \text{ grad}^2$ will bring down momentum squared. (See notes [1] and [2] for a discussion of the probabilistic nature of $W(x)$ and a description attempting to assign $W(x)^2$ to a physical density.) Thus:

$$V(x) W(x) = (E - 1/2m \text{ grad}^2) W(x) \text{ which is the Schrodinger equation.}$$

This helps to explain why the Fourier series of $W(x)$, called the wavefunction in quantum mechanics, has physical meaning. Normally, it would simply be a mathematical series. It is argued that this meaning comes from its nature as a "potential" i.e. $-grad$ brings down the momentum. This is interesting because it implies that there is an eigenvalue equation, namely

$grad W(x)$ is proportional to average momentum

Conclusion

In conclusion, considering a potential $V(x)$ as a source of momentum "kicks", described by its Fourier series can possibly lead to the Schrodinger equation. One first assumes that the potential stirs up an ensemble $W(x)$ of different momenta. This ensemble itself, however, seems to act like a source of momentum "kicks" with different relative probabilities and so should also be written as a Fourier series. Multiplying the two Fourier series $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ should yield a third "potential" like ensemble which should be equal to $W(x)$, up to a constant, if there is equilibrium. Noting that $V(x)$ is equal to energy - average Kinetic energy leads to the Schrodinger equation.

References

- [1] Francesco R. Ruggeri . Wavefunction Squared As Spatial Probability Zenodo 2018.
- [2] Francesco R. Ruggeri InW As a Partition Function. Zenodo Sept. 2018;
- [3] U. Klein. The Statistical Origins of Quantum Mechanics. Physics Research International Volume 2010, Article ID 808424, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2010/808424>
- [4] Francesco R. Ruggeri Is Quantum Mechanics Contained in Special Relativity? Zenodo 2018.